

GRANULOMETRIC COMPOSITION OF IRRIGATED MEADOW SAZ SOILS DISTRIBUTED IN THE TERRITORIES OF DANGARA AND FURKAT DISTRICTS

D. Kholdarov¹, D. Karimova²

DSc in Biological sciences, associate professor, Fergana State University¹

Basic Doctoral Student, Kokand State University²

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Abstract. *This article examines the granulometric composition of irrigated meadow-marsh soils with varying degrees of salinity in the territories of Dangara and Furkat districts. Among the agrophysical properties of soils, the granulometric composition is a key indicator that determines the water-physical, air and thermal regimes, as well as the distribution of humus and nutrient elements. The research was conducted following the methodology of the former Uzbek Cotton-Growing Research Institute. Chemical analyses were carried out according to the procedure of E.V. Arinushkina, and the results were processed by the dispersion method using B.A. Dospekhov's manual and Microsoft Excel. The obtained data show that, as the degree of salinity increases, the fraction of physical clay in the soil profile changes and the proportion of physical sand in the lower layers rises. The increasing heaviness of the granulometric composition in the upper layers directly affects the movement of water-soluble salts and the amount of humus in the soil. These findings are of significant theoretical and practical importance for improving the fertility of saline lands and for planning effective land-reclamation measures.*

Keywords: *meadow saz, granulometric composition, parent rock, element, chemical composition, salinization, sand, clay, layer, accumulation.*

INTRODUCTION

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of 7 February 2017 «On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan» [1], and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 903 of 2 February 2024 “On Protecting Soil and Increasing its Fertility” [2] were adopted. In this regard, an important task before us is to enrich soils with humus and with the amounts of chemical nutrient elements. One of the most important agrophysical properties of soil is its granulometric composition. The granulometric composition of soil influences its water-physical, air, thermal, chemical, agrochemical and microbiological properties and determines the standards for carrying out agrotechnological measures. One of the most important agrophysical properties of soil is its granulometric composition. The granulometric composition of soil affects its water-physical, air, thermal, chemical, agrochemical, and microbiological properties and determines the standards for carrying out agrotechnological measures.

The granulometric composition of soil plays a decisive role in the manifestation of a number of its properties. Determining the granulometric composition by soil horizons is important for studying the origin of soils, because it depends not only on the composition of the parent material but also on the processes of soil formation occurring within the soil itself. In particular, such characteristics as soil porosity, capillary rise of moisture, the amount of nutrient elements, moisture capacity, and water permeability directly depend on the granulometric composition of

the soil. There is also a certain degree of correlation between the granulometric composition and the content of mobile nutrient elements.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In our country and abroad, a number of scientific studies have been carried out to investigate the mechanical and general physical properties of soils, among which we can mention the research conducted by [3; 4; 5], [6], [7], [8; 9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14] and others. There is a certain relationship between the mineralogical, mechanical, and chemical composition of soft rocks. The effect of granulometric composition on soil temperature is associated with the thermal properties of light and heavy soils. In spring, when moisture content is high, clay soils—where heat is consumed for evaporation—warm up more slowly than light soils. Because soil layers differ in their granulometric composition, their water permeability is not the same.

R. Qurvantaev noted that the mechanical and microaggregate composition of soil is a key indicator of its morphological, reclamation, hydro-physical and physico-mechanical properties, as well as of soil bonitation, and that it reflects specific features characteristic of all genetic horizons of various soil types and subtypes [4]. The air regime of soils is also directly dependent on their granulometric composition. The denser the soil, the less air it contains. For example, sandy soil contains more air because it is looser than clay soil.

In classifying the mechanical elements of soil, the classifications of N.A. Kachinskiy and the Uzbek Research Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry (O'zPITI) are widely used. Knowing the size of the particles that make up the soil and their proportions has great theoretical and practical significance. G.T. Parpiev, R.K. Kuziev, and R. Qurvantaev noted that the gray oasis soils possess various types of granulometric composition and that, according to the structure of the lithological profile, their characteristics are mainly homogeneous, while in some cases they consist of different multilayered granulometric compositions [8].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

During the research, the field studies were conducted based on the “Methodology of conducting field experiments” of the former Uzbek Cotton Growing Research Institute, and analyzes were conducted based on “Guidelines for the chemical analysis of soils” by E.V. Arinushkina. The mathematical-statistical analyses of the results obtained were calculated by the dispersion method using the manual "Methods of field experience" by B.A. Dospekhov and Microsoft Excel.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The irrigated meadow soils with varying degrees of salinity found in the territories of Dangara and Furkat districts consist, in terms of granulometric composition, of sandy loam as well as light and medium loam. These irrigated meadow soils are mainly distributed in the middle parts of the Sox River alluvial fan and are composed of sandy loam and light loam. In other sections of these soils, the upper layers are of medium loam, while downward they are formed of heavy loam and clay layers, and below 140–170 cm an alluvial sandy layer is observed.

In the non-saline irrigated meadow soils, the amount of physical clay in the plough layer and the sub-plough layer is 27.9–43.1% (Figure 1), consisting of light and medium loam. Toward the lower layers, the amount of physical clay decreases while the amount of physical sand increases, making up 26.8% light loam at the 70–100 cm layer, 23.2% light loam at the 100–135 cm layer, and 18.5% sandy loam at the 135–180 cm layer (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Non-saline meadow saz soils of the "Adolat Yogdusi Nuri" farm, Dangara district

In the slightly saline irrigated meadow saz soils, the amount of physical clay in the plough layer and sub-plough layer is 28.7–25.6% (Figure 2), consisting of light loam. Toward the lower layers, the amount of physical sand decreases while the amount of physical clay increases: in the 65–95 cm layer it reaches 41.5% medium loam, in the 95–135 cm layer 39.6% medium loam, and in the 140–175 cm layer 17.6% sandy loam (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Slightly saline meadow saz soils of the "Hayratul Orol" farm, Dangara district

The granulometric composition of moderately saline irrigated meadow saz soils includes layers of light loam, medium loam, and sandy loam. In the plough layer and sub-plough layer of these soils, the amount of physical clay is 27.9–26.2% with a light loam texture (Figure 3). In the 65–90 cm layer it is 22.4% light loam, in the 90–145 cm layer 39.6% medium loam, and in the 145–180 cm layer 14.3% sandy loam (Figure 3).

The granulometric composition of strongly saline irrigated meadow saz soils is diverse, ranging from sandy loam to sand; within the soil profile, layers of light and medium loam are also present. In the plough and sub-plough layers of these strongly saline soils, the amount of physical clay is 16.9–27.0%, corresponding to sandy loam and light loam (Figure 4). In the 60–90 cm layer

it is 26.3% light loam, in the 90–140 cm layer 40.1% medium loam, and in the 140–170 cm layer 6.7% sand (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Moderately saline meadow saz soils of the "Jamshidbek" farm, Furkat district

Figure 4. Strongly saline meadow saz soils of the "Bahoroy-Shoxinabonu kelajagi" farm, Furkat district

These particles determine the structure of the soil as well as its physical and chemical properties. The granulometric composition of these soils differs slightly from that of the parent material that formed them. The reason for this is the prevailing wind erosion in the area: due to the frequent movement of sand dunes, the granulometric composition of the upper soil layers' changes over time. The difference in the meadow saz soils is expressed by the higher content of physical clay in the parent material. In irrigated soils, the washing of the silt fraction down to the lower layers results in the formation of lessivage. In fact, the granulometric composition of soils is normally similar to that of the parent material. However, in irrigated areas exposed to strong wind erosion this regularity is disturbed. Over many years, the turbidity of irrigation water enriches and makes the soil's granulometric composition heavier through the addition of silt and colloidal particles. At the same time, the formation of the agro-irrigation layer reduces the contrast between the layers' granulometric composition and makes them heavier. As the duration of irrigation increases, the granulometric composition of the soil becomes progressively heavier [15, 16, 17].

CONCLUSION

From the presented data, it can be noted that as the period of cultivation of meadow saz soils with different degrees of salinity increases, the granulometric composition of their upper layers becomes heavier. This, in turn, is also reflected in the content of humus and nutrient elements in the soil. The concentration of the soil solution, the soil's ability to retain water-soluble salts, and their movement also occur depending on the granulometric composition.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 7-fevraldagi PF-4947-son. «O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha harakatlar strategiyasi to'g'risida»gi Farmoni. Lex.uz
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasining 2024-yil 2-fevraldagi 903-son «Tuproqni muhofaza qilish va uning unumdorligini oshirish to'g'risida»gi qonuni. Lex.uz
3. Курвантаев Р., Назарова С.М. Агрофизическая характеристика орошаемых луговых почв Бухарского оазиса / Современные тенденции в научном обеспечении агропромышленного комплекса. Коллективная монография. – Иваново, 2019. – С.91-95.
4. Курвантаев Р., Назарова С., Солиева Н., Истамова М. Қоракўл воҳаси суғориладиган ўтлоқи тупроқларининг механик ва микроагрегат таркибини антропоген омиллар таъсирида ўзгариши // Тупроқшunoslik va agrokimyo. – 2023. – №1. – Б.50-55.
5. Курвантаев Р., Норкулов З.Э., Файзиев К.И. Хоразм воҳаси тупроқларининг механик ва микроагрегат таркиби // Хоразм Ма'mun Akademiyasi axborotnomasi. – 2019. – №6/1. – Б.66-71.
6. Абдурахмонов Н.Ю., Собитов У.Т., Курдашев К.Д. Агрофизические свойства в различной степени гипсированных орошаемых лугово-сероземных почв // Научное обозрение. Биологические науки. – 2024. – №1 – С.5-11
7. Артикова Х.Т. Бухоро воҳаси суғориладиган ўтлоқи аллювиал тупроқларининг умумий физик ва айрим сув-физик хоссалари, уларнинг аҳамияти // ЎзМУ хабарлари. – 2018. – №3/1. – Б.47-51.
8. Парпиев Г.Т., Кузиев Р.К., Курвантаев Р.К. Особенности структурного состава оазисных почв регионов Узбекистана // Научное обозрение. Биологические науки. – Москва, 2019. – №2. – С.20-24.
9. Парпиев Г.Т. Мирзачўл воҳаси тупроқлари механик, микро- ва макроагрегат таркибларининг суғориш таъсирида ўзгариши / Тупроқшунослик – мамлакат экологик ва озиқ-овқат хавфсизлиги хизматида. – Тошкент, 2017. – Б.142-146.
10. Джалилова Г.Т. Механический состав горных почв в зависимости от рельефа и экспозиции склона // Хоразм Ма'mun Akademiyasi axborotnomasi. – 2018. – №2. – С.87-90.
11. Бердиев Т. Т. Сурхон-Шеробод воҳаси чўл минтақаси суғориладиган тупроқларининг айрим физик, сув-физик хоссалари // ЎзМУ хабарлари. – Ташкент, 2017. – №3/1. – Б.26-30.
12. Назарова С.М. Бухоро воҳаси суғориладиган ўтлоқи тупроқларининг ҳозирги давр агрофизикавий ҳолати. Қишлоқ хўжалиги фанлари бўй.фалс.д-ри ... дисс. автореф. – Тошкент, 2019. – 44 б.

13. Ҳакимова Н.Х. Зарафшон дарёси қуёи ва ўрта оқими тупроқларининг агрофизикавий хоссалари ва биологик фаоллиги: Биология фанлари бўйича фалсафа д-ри ... дисс. автореф. – Фарғона, 2022. – 44 б.
14. Алибоева М., Жаббаров З., Фахрутдинова М. Чотқол давлат биосфераси кўриқхонаси ҳудуди тупроқларининг физик хоссаларига гумуснинг таъсири // Агро процессинг журнали. – Тошкент, 2022. – №2, Том 4. – Б.46-51.
15. Kholdarov D. Current state of saline soils in the Fergana Valley. E3S Web of Conferences 563, 03053 (2024). ICESTE 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202456303053>
16. Kholdarov D. Saline Soils and Alkali Soils of the Fergana Valley and Ways to Improve Them. NATURALISTA CAMPANO. ISSN: 1827-7160. Volume 28 Issue 2, 2024. <https://museonaturalistico.it>. PP. 281-288
17. Xoldarov D. M., Karimova D.F. Furqat va Beshariq tumani sug'oriladigan o'tloqi saz tuproqlarining agrokimyoviy xossalari. "ЎзМУ хабарлари" журнали. 2025 йил 3/1/1-сон, 147-150 Б.